

Complexation Reaction of Metal Ions with Peptide Systems. Part--X : Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Some Rare Earth Complexes with Glycyl-L-Proline

RANJIT SINGH SANDHU and RANJIT KUMAR KALIA

Chemistry Department, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar-148 005

Manuscript received 20 September 1980, revised 17 March 1982, accepted 28 September 1982

Complexes of Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III) and Yb(III) with glycyl-L-proline have been investigated by the potentiometric titration technique in aqueous medium at $\mu=0.15 M$ (KNO_3). The proton-ligand stability constants and formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique. The log K values have been determined by different methods. The overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have also been evaluated.

THE metal complexes of amino acids and peptides have been of interest to both coordination chemists and biochemists for a long time¹. A survey of literature revealed that extensive studies^{2,3} have been made on the complexation of amino acids and peptides with different metal ions. Recently, the present authors⁴ reported the stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) complexes with glycyl-L-proline. The present investigation deals with the potentiometric studies on complexes of Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III) and Yb(III) with glycyl-L-proline. The stability constants have been determined in aqueous media at $\mu=0.15 M$ (KNO_3) at 25, 35 and 45° from which ΔG has also been evaluated. The method of Calvin-Bjerrum^{5,6} as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁷ has been employed to determine the parameters.

Experimental

The ligand, glycyl-L-proline was obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories and was dried at 100° for 24 hr. Fresh ligand solution (0.025 M) was prepared just before use in double distilled water.

Metal nitrates were prepared by the action of nitric acid on the corresponding AnalaR grade metal oxides and their purity was checked by EDTA titration. Stock solutions (0.005 M) of metal nitrates were prepared in double distilled water. Carbonate-free potassium hydroxide (0.0526 M) solution was prepared by Vogel's method⁸. Nitric acid (0.0051 M), potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M), potassium nitrate (1 M) and borax (0.01 M), all of B.D.H. AnalaR grade, were prepared in double distilled water. A Photovolt digicord pH meter having a sensitivity of ± 0.002 pH unit was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffers before use. All titrations were carried out in a thermostated bath maintained at 25 ± 0.1 , 35 ± 0.1 or $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The details of procedure and calculations of $\bar{n}$, pL and thermodynamic functions are as described elsewhere⁹.

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand stability constants and thermodynamic functions are summarized in

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND, METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AT THREE TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Metal ion	Constants	Temperature°C			$-\Delta G(K \text{ cal/mole})$ at °C			ΔH (K cal/mole) at 35°C	ΔS (Cal/mole/degree) at 35°C
		25	35	45	25	35	45		
H ⁺	$\log^p K_1^H$	8.55	8.40	8.23					
Sm(III)	$\log K_1$	3.80	3.98	4.05	5.18	5.54	5.89	5.5	35.8
Gd(III)	$\log K_1$	3.74	3.88	3.98	5.10	5.40	5.79	5.3	34.8
Dy(III)	$\log K_1$	3.94	4.05	4.18	5.97	5.71	6.08	5.3	35.7
Er(III)	$\log K_1$	4.02	4.12	4.23	5.48	5.81	6.16	4.6	38.8
Yb(III)	$\log K_1$	4.10	4.20	4.33	5.59	5.92	6.30	5.0	35.5

Table 1. The mole ratio of metal of glycyl-L-proline was kept at 1 : 5 in order to satisfy the maximum coordination number of the metal ion. In the initial stages of titration, the ligand titration curve shifts to the left of the acid titration curve due to the acceptance of a proton by the amino group from the strongly acidic medium. The neutralization of the -COOH group of the zwitterion is completed where the ligand curve crosses the acid curve. The further course of the ligand curve is due to neutralization of a second proton from the ligand. The other curves are of usual shape.

The mean value of $\log {}^pK_1^H$ at 25, 35 and 45° are 8.55, 8.40 and 8.23, respectively. The value of $\log {}^pK_1^H = 8.55$ at 25° is within the limits of error (± 0.05) of the value reported in the literature^{10,11}. The value of $\log {}^pK_1^H$ decreases with increase in temperature.

The formation curve for the metal-ligand complex was obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ versus pL . The values of $\bar{n}$ obtained indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Er(III) and Yb(III) with glycyl-L-proline. The overall stability at these temperatures is Yb(III) > Er(III) > Dy(III) > Gd(III) < Sm(III). There is a dip in $\log K_1$ value at Gd(III), which may be attributed to its electronic configuration.

The values of ΔH show that reactions of these metals with glycyl-L-proline are endothermic. Since

the complex formation reaction is favoured by higher temperature, the value of $\log K_1$ increases with temperature. In all the systems the entropy change (ΔS) is positive and favours complex formation. The values of free energies of formation become more negative with increase in temperature which indicates that the complex formation becomes more spontaneous with temperature.

References

1. G. L. EICHERON, "Inorganic Biochemistry", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1973, Vol. 1.
2. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", The Chemical Society, London, Special Publication No. 17, 1964.
3. L. G. SILLEN and A. E. MARTELL, "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", The Chemical Society, London, Special Publication No. 25, 1971.
4. R. S. SANDHU, RAKESH KUMAR and R. K. KALIA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1979, 30, 355.
5. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Copenhagen, 1941.
7. H. IRVING and H. S. RUSSELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1961, p. 242.
9. S. D. MAKIJANI and S. P. SANGAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 670.
10. M. K. KIM and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 914; 1967, 89, 5138.
11. R. B. MARTIN, M. CHAMBERLIN and J. T. EDSALL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 495.